

THE CONTRAST OF THE COMPLEX SENTENCE: THE CASE OF ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to analyse the compound and the complex sentence between Albanian and English language. In Albanian and English, we have some kinds of compound sentences. So, between two languages we have the contrast structure. The complex sentence is like a simple sentence but the different is that has one or more subordinate clause functioning than the simple sentence.

Keywords: Compound Sentence, Contrast, Function.

INTRODUCTION

The mayor types of multiple sentences are the compound and the complex.

In a compound sentence the immediate constituents are two or more coordinate clause. In a complex sentence one or more of its elements, such as direct object or adverbial, are realized by a subordinate (Randolph Q., 1985). In Albanian and English this type is productive. The complex sentence is like a simple sentence but the different is that has one or more subordinate clause functioning than the simple sentence. In both of languages the noun is the head of sentence.

We have four kinds of compound Sentence:

- a. **Independent compound sentence** (Albanian conjunction and English: **e, edhe, dhe, as, por, mirëpo, ndërsa, po, kurse, edhe...edhe, as...as...** etc, or English *and, but, yet, so etc*).
- b. **Dependent compound sentence** (Albanian conjunction and English: **sepse, nëse, që, se, sikur, si, po, se, ngaqë, if, because, that, how, however** etc.
- c. The compound sentence with semicolon don't have co-ordinates, such as (**and, but, so, because, if** etc.)
- d. The compound complex sentence.

Compound sentences consist of two or more independent clauses that can make of coordinating conjunctions e.g.

Ajo e ka dëgjuar një zë poshtë dhe i ka telefonuar prindrit e saj.

She heard a noise downstairs **and** phoned her parents.

Teuta nuk shkoi në shkollë **sepse** ajo ishte e sëmurë

Teuta didn't go to school **because** she was ill.

His father used to be rich **and** he will buy a new car.

I don't like dogs, **and** my sister doesn't like cats.

You can write on paper, **or** you can use a computer.

A tree fell onto the school roof in a storm, **but** none of the students was injured.

The noun in the simple, complex or compound sentence usually is subject, object etc. Contains two independent clauses that are joined by a coordinating conjunction. The most common coordinating conjunctions are: (Alb.) **dhe, e, edhe, as, as as...**, – (eng.) **and, or, but, so...** etc).

A. I feel to speak **Albanian**, and **my friend** feels to speak **English**.

S P DO S P DO

Beni played **football**, **so I** went **at school**.

S P DO S P DO

The **compound sentence** is a combination of two or more simple sentence or complex sentences. While the complex sentence has only *one* main clause, the compound has *two or more* independent clauses making statements, questions, or commands.

A compound sentence usually consists of more than one simple sentence (clause). All of the clauses in a compound sentence are independent and they are usually bound by co-coordinators, such as, and, but or and their substitutes e.g.

Everyone was in the hall and the door had been closed (Veseli N., 2002).

The compound sentences in Albanian language are: (in the following all the noun we will underline)

- a. **Dikush** këndonte dhe të tjerët flisnin ngadalë.

S S DO

- b. **Shiu** kishte pushuar dhe **qielli** ishte kthjellur.

- c. **Koha** ishte me shi dhe **Beni** dhe unë shpejtuam hapin dhe pas pak dëgjuam disa zëra duke ma thirrur, por ne nuk u ndalem, sepse nuk ia besonim se do të ndalet shiu.

- d. **Peshku** në det e filterja në zjarr.

By the Albanian sentences we can consider the noun is subject, direct and indirect object and predicate in the compound sentence. It is the same and in English language but of course with some different structure of using e.g.

A write with strong intelligence but weak invention is not likely to become a novelist. The Reverend Mr. Gaster begins Peacock's series of gourmandizing clergymen's Panscope is his first and thinnest burlesque of Coleridge's transcendentalism (Thomas Love P. 2002).

Arta suppose that she can use phone.

In a few minutes I'll ask him what he wants tomorrow.

Beni speaks English, but Tomi speaks Albanian.

Beni reads a book, however Arta reads a newspaper.

Toni reads newspaper, his friend reads magazine.

Arta supozon se ajo mund ta përdorë telefonin.

Për pak minuta unë do ta pyes atë çka ai dëshiron të bën nesër.

Complex Sentences (fjali me nënrenditje) consist of a main clause with one or more subordinate clause. In both of languages this form of sentence is still complex by the structure.

The sentence **"People know voters prefer results"** has this notation; the rules isolated in the preceding paragraph can be stated as follows:

S → NP VP

NP → N

NP → S

N → people, voters, results

V → know, prefer. The diagram of the notation of the sentence is:

People know voters prefer results

Figure 1

The rules of Albanian and English grammar can be considered to description which assigns the structure or diagram. The noun phrase in English and Albanian is more productive if we study with the rule of generative and diagram, too (and we would like to following this way).

The noun is the same with function how is in the simple sentence (It can be subject, direct or indirect object, predicate etc.).

Beni reads **newspaper**, *because* **the book** is difficult.

Beni lexon **gazetën**, sepse **libri** është i vështirë.

This sentence is making by two sentences and the second is dependent clause.

Ne do të vazhdojmë të luajmë futboll, **nëse** Agroni nuk vonohet.

I met him **when** I was at the university.

In Albanian and English, we have a lot of **subordinating conjunctions** and by those we can know the form of structure.

A complex sentence has an independent clause joined by one or more dependent clauses. A complex sentence always has a subordinator such as **because, since, after, although**, or when or a relative pronoun such as **that, who, which** e.g.

The students are studying **because** they have a test tomorrow.

Studentët janë duke studiuar **sepse** kanë test nesër.

Arta and Beni went to the movies **after** they finished studying.

In describing the noun phrases or *the head, around which the other constituents cluster and which dictates concord with other parts of the sentence*:

*The tall **girl** standing in the corner is my **sister**.*

*The tall **girls** standing in the corner are my **sisters**.*

*[The tall **girl** standing (**which or who**) has a blue sweaterë is my **sister**.*

I saw the tall **girl** in [the corner (**which or who**) was full of **people**.

In Albanian and English, the complex sentence has one or more independent clause and one or more dependent clauses e.g.

Nuk ishte vështirë të parandalohet **ç'qëndrim do të mbanin ata** dhe **ç'vendim do të merrnin**.

This sentence ka has this tree of diagram:

Figure 2

This Albanian language the sentence is the complex that has one head sentence (**Nuk ishte vështirë**) and three another's sentences which are dependents how are seeing by the tree of diagram. Complex sentences use subordination to show the relative importance of ideas in a sentence.

In Albanian language, in this way is possible to generate simple and compound sentence, like with: “**Studenti kishte takuar profesorin para provimit**”. It can generate with the diagram and the noun is the head (S) of the sentence. The (follow) tree of diagram is studied by **Josif Mita e.g.**

Figure 3

This diagram is opposite with the Chomsky message. This study is impossible to have the meaning because the first this is simple sentence and it needs to generation with the form NP + VP - NP or the right tree for this sentence is more possible this on:

Figure 4

As we said before the noun is the head of sentence, because it can be a **subject, direct and indirect object** etc e.g. **Studenti kishte takuar profesorin para provimit.**

S P IO DO

The Albanian sentence “Kur deti egërsuhej peshkatarët rrinin në shtëpi”

SE + (FN) + SF+S' → S'+SE+ (FN) +SF
 1 2 → 2 1

Figure 5

I think this diagram is not correct because it is the compound sentence. The symbol **Fj** need to be **P.N.k.** (periudhë -**P** – compound sentence and nënrenditur -**N** -suborder, kohore -**k** -time), after **SE** “peshkatarët” cannot stay in the middle of the diagram. The **SF** cannot be there but I think it is the second sentence (**Fj2**). I think the correct analyse for this diagram is:

Figure 6

The Albanian compound sentence “Nëna gëzohej që i ishte bërë vajza për shkollë” is possible to generate in this way: P.F.N.sh (Fj1 – SE + SF – që - Fj2 SF+SE).

Figure 7

The same diagram is possible to have:

Figure 8

Figure 9

The Albanian compound sentence *Ushtarët u ulën, ndezën zjarrin dhe disa zunë të hanë nga strajca që kishin më vete* can generate in this diagram:

Figure 10

The next Albanian sentence can generate as:

Kanë parë Agimin dhe kanë përshëndetur Luanin.

Figure 11

The last diagram was presented by Josif Mita at his book “Hyrje në sintaksën gjenerative” f. 210, but I think the correct way for to present is:

The diagram of the notation of the sentence is:

Figure 13

The rules of Albanian and English grammar can be considered to description which assigns the structure or diagram. The noun phrase in English and Albanian is more productive if we study and respect the rules of generative and diagrams, too. The contrast of genitive between Albanian and English (word) can be in the sentence at the beginning, middle or in the end. The tree or diagram of the simple sentence can follow the genitive that is in the beginning of sentence:

Figure 14

This diagram of the sentence “**The students’** hands **the teacher their quizzes**” the genitive is the subject “the students’” and it is not correct with the indirect object, because it needs to be one tree by noun phrase and from it to generate direct or indirect object.

CONCLUSION

As the interdiction in English language, we have a lot of same sentences that the head is the noun e.g. John has worked in New York, because he liked it. The function of noun in the simple or compound sentence can be subject, direct or indirect object, predicate nominal etc. The noun is the head in the sentence and can be complement in the simple or compound sentence. The recommendation of this paper provides analysis of the simple, compound or complex sentence. The synthetic structure of Albanian language compared to English language is possible to be generated and compared between two languages as in fig. number from 1 to 13. Two languages have the contrast in morphology, in all categories (nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs ...) and however, it is possible to find contrast in all parts of speech that are in the function of the sentence such as subject, predicate, direct object or indirect object.

References

- 1) Carnie, A. (2002). Syntax. Oxford.
- 2) Radford, A. (2004). English Syntax. Cambridge.
- 3) Radford, A. (1997). Syntactic theory and the structure of English. Cambridge.
- 4) Radford, A. (2004). English syntax. Cambridge.
- 5) Aronoff, M. (1992). Morphology now, State University of New York.
- 6) Aronoff, M. (1975). Word Formation in Generative Grammar. Cambridge.
- 7) Baker, C.L. (1995). English Syntax. London.
- 8) Grup autoresh. (2002). Gramatika e Gjuhës shqipe I. Tiranë.
- 9) Grup autoresh. (2002). Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe II. Tiranë.
- 10) Ian, R. (1997). Comparative Syntax. London.
- 11) Lilane, H. (1997). The New Comparative syntax. London.
- 12) Lynn, B. (1999). English syntax. New York.
- 13) Lyons, J. (1970). Generative Syntax. Harmondsworth.
- 14) Lyons, J. (1984). Language Linguistics. Cambridge University Pres.
- 15) Matthews, P.H. (1984). Syntax, Cambridge.
- 16) Chomsky, N. (2002). Syntactic Structures. New York.
- 17) Chomsky, N. (2007). Language and problems of knowledge, (përkth. në shqip Blerta Topalli). Tiranë.
- 18) Culicover, P. (1992). Syntax. London.
- 19) Culicover, P. (2005). Simple syntax. Oxford.
- 20) Culicover, P. (2007). Simpler syntax. Oxford.

- 21) Sgall, P (...). (1968). A functional approach to syntax, in generative description of language. New York.
- 22) Qesku, P. (2002). Fjalor Anglisht-Shqip, English-Albanian Dictionary. Tiranë.
- 23) Raymond, M. (1986). English Grammar in Use. Cambridge.
- 24) Millaku, Sh. (2015). Kërkime gjuhësore. Prizren.
- 25) Millaku, Sh. (2011). Studime gjuhësore I. Prishtinë.
- 26) Millaku, Sh. (2011). Strukturat sintaksore. Prishtinë.
- 27) Millaku, Sh. (2009). (Profesor Selman Riza dhe Albanologjia) Studimet e
- 28) Shkelqim Millaku, The contrast of Direct Object between Albanian and English language
- 29) ISSN: 2454-1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in> - <http://www.onlinejournal.in/IJIRV2I7/253.pdf>
- 30) Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, Dubai, 2016.
- 31) Shkelqim Millaku, The contrast of the gender between Albanian and
- 32) English language, International Journal of Thales Educational Sciences (THEDS) ISSN (print): 2149-5130 - http://media.wix.com/ugd/d4d001_2582d04ef0264786b60ca6e76227ebc3.pdf 1-15; Vol.2, No.1, Turqi, 2016.
- 33) Millaku, Shkelqim, 2015, The Compound Nouns,
- 34) https://www.academia.edu/6091482/The_Compound_Nouns
- 35) Millaku, Shkelqim, 2016, The Noun Phrases, Anglisticum Journal,
- 36) <http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/viewFile/580/647>
- 37) Millaku, Shkelqim: The Nominal Clause and the Noun Phrases: A Comparative Study of Albanian and English, World Journal of English Language Vol. 12, No. 2; 2022, Special Issue.
- 38) <https://www.sciedupress.com/journal/index.php/wjel/article/view/21679/13415>
- 39) Millaku, Shkelqim, 2015, The Direct Object, Anglisticum Journal,
- 40) <http://anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>, Retrieved on February 17, 2016.
- 41) Millaku, Shkelqim, 2015, The Genitive, Anglisticum Journal
- 42) <http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/156> Retrieved on February 17, 2016.
- 43) Shkelqim Millaku, Inclusion And The Historical Development Of The Albanian Generative Concepts, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>
- 44) Shkelqim Millaku, The Contrast Of The Compound Words Between English And Albanian Language, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: www.oapub.org/edu, <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
- 45) https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614
- 46) Shkelqim Millaku, The Indirect Object (Io) – Albanian And English, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/294>
- 47) Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-8187 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>

- 48) Shkelqim Millaku, The Contrast Of The Compound Words Between English And Albanian Language, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>
- 49) https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051614
- 50) Shkelqim Millaku, Inclusion And The Historical Development Of The Albanian Generative Concepts, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>
- 51) Shkelqim Millaku, The Function Of Albanian And English Sentence, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>
- 52) Shkelqim Millaku, Inclusion And The Historical Development Of The Albanian Generative Concepts, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching ISSN: 2537 - 1754 ISSN-L: 2537 - 1754, <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/1139/3304>
- 53) Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, Anglisticum. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-8187 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179,
- 54) <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>
- 55) Shkelqim Millaku, The Function Of Albanian And English Sentence, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/830/2369>
- 56) Shkelqim Millaku, The Function Of Noun Phrases Between Albanian And English, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051611
- 57) Shkelqim Millaku, The contrast of the gender between Albanian and English language, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3041938
- 58) Shkelqim Millaku, The Contrast And The Function Of The Gender Albanian To English Language, European Journal of English Language Teaching ISSN: 2501-7136 ISSN-L: 2501-7136 Available on-line at: <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejel/article/view/829/2366>
- 59) Shkelqim Millaku, The direct object, Anglisticum. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, Volume 4, issue 1, 2015 • e-ISSN: 1857-8187 • p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/233>
- 60) Shkelqim Millaku, The Nominal Clauses of English and Albanian Language, Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR) Vol-3, Issue-8, 2017 ISSN: 2454-1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in,http://www.imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/viewFile/5472/5264>
- 61) Mann, S. A. (1932). Short Albanian grammar. London.
- 62) Jupp, T.C & John Milne. (1968). English sentence structure. London.
- 63) Harris, Z. (1951). Structural linguistic. London.